

Student Assessment under Complex Thinking: Driving gamified self-made Students' summative assessment (gSSA)

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Abstract

This study presents a method for creating summative assessments by the students, under the Complex Thinking approach. As an innovation, the method requires students to propose their summative assessment questions, which is made possible through the gamification learning strategy. A case study describes the aspects of the experiment, the method development stages, and the results obtained. The experiment development occurred during the first semester in a theoretical discipline called "Organisational Administration", where the four functions of Administration are studied in the bachelor's degree in Information Systems at the Instituto Federal Fluminense. In the traditional learning methods, expositive classes are the usual approach for theoretical disciplines like "Organisational Administration." In this case, the flipped classroom and problem-based learning were adopted as an active learning approach and diagnostic and formative assessments. Then, the summative assessment described in this study was not more important than the other assessments, as usually happens with traditional learning methods. The findings suggest that the technique was highly successful in fostering playful student engagement. Additionally, it alleviated the teacher's workload by decentralising the summative assessment elaboration. Finally, the experiment shows how it is possible to promote students' assessment according to the Complex Thinking premises.

Keywords: Summative Assessment; Active Learning; Gamification.

1 Introduction

Student assessment is a challenge for teachers and educational institutions. This challenge is scaffolded by some driven questions, such as: How could students be assessed to verify their knowledge? What would be the right way to assess the students? In addition, more in-depth, what is the real purpose of student assessment in a Complex (Morin, 2001) context?

Teachers, institutions, and students are increasingly concerned about the limitations of traditional expositive learning methods (TELM) in meeting the professional and academic demands of the 21st century. However, recent research has brought excellent results related to adopting active learning approaches (ALA), such as flipped classrooms, gamification, project-based learning, problem-based learning, and more (Alves & van-Hattum-Janssen, 2022; Rieg et al. 2022; Lima et al. 2024).

In the TELM, student assessment is not considered a challenge by the teachers and institutions due to the worry of applying one-off summative content assessments in most cases with objective and discursive questions. In this case, the major concern is to prepare questions that are difficult enough to prevent students from correctly answering the question without a minimum of reflection.

However, the fact is that, like the TELM, the one-off summative content assessments (OOSCA) cartesianiously verify a very small aspect of student knowledge: their capability to memorise or reflect on some concept. Doing this, exist an overvaluation of technical competencies to the detriment of their social abilities and professional skills, which are ignored in this type of assessment (Kleim, 2000; Felder & Silverman, 1988).

Since teachers have adopted ALA, the dimension of students' assessment has become more complex because the assessment cannot be limited to a content approach as adopted in the TELM. For the ALA, OOSCA is only one of the different ways to assess the students, not having the same importance attributed to it in the TELM (Fernandes et al., 2021).

Despite OOSCA having less importance for ALA than TELM, it does not mean that OOSCA is unimportant. However, a simple adoption of OOSCA for ALA (as is being adopted in TELM) seems to be a poor way to take the potentialities of ALA. For example, OOSCA/TELM only consider students as passive characters of the learning process because they only answer the objective or discursive questions made by the teacher.

In the context of ALA, where summative assessment is only a part of a range of assessment ways like self-assessment, peer assessment, and external assessment, this paper proposes a gamified self-made students' summative assessment (gSSA). In this, the students have become the protagonist, developing their summative assessment through gamification. This proposal was applied in a case study: a cohort from the discipline "Organisational Administration".

This paper is structured in five sections. This introduction is followed by Section 2, which contains the concepts of assessment and its types, as well as the concept of gamification as a learning approach. Section 3 brings the gSSA for summative assessment development in the context of ALA. In Section 4, the results are presented. In Section 5, a discussion is undertaken, followed by the conclusion in Section 6.

2 Study Context

This section brings the theoretical concepts related to the present research: assessment strategies and gamification concepts.

2.1 Student assessment strategies under Complex Thinking

Assessment is inherent to a learning process that can be considered as a feedback message about how students should fit into the learning (Uebe-Mansur & Alves, 2018). From our first breath as a learning person, the assessment is there, allowing us to grow and become professionals who will continuously be trained and assessed in the workplace (Uebe-Mansur & Alves, 2020). However, independently of the context, it is always complex and, most of the time, students feel unfairness, frustration, and demotivation among others. Involving the assessed persons (students, trainees) could reduce these sentiments.

Complexity or Complex Thinking is a way of thinking about life and its things that emphasizes the interconnectedness in contrast to the fragmenting thought of Cartesians proposed by the philosopher Rene Descartes. Complex Thinking seeks to stitch together that was fragmented by Cartesian reductionist thinking, seeing the complexity of real-world phenomena, rejecting simplistic reductionist approaches. Instead advocating for a holistic understanding that considers multiple perspectives, interactions, and levels of analysis within a system. Essentially, it is a way of thinking that acknowledges the intricate nature of reality and avoids oversimplification by integrating diverse factors and considering the dynamic relationships between them (Morin, 2007; Morin and Mortuori, 2008).

At the same time, this could be reduced by applying different assessment strategies as they assume different roles. These assessment roles are grouped, mainly, into two categories: 1) summative assessment and 2) formative assessment (Hadji, 1994). According to Fernandes et al. (2021), the summative assessment goal is to certify, compare and select, while formative assessment aims to monitor, guide, improve, support and regulate student learning. These assessment roles are also related to different types of assessment methods: traditional methods, which include tests and examinations, related to summative assessment, and alternative or student-

centred methods, for example, portfolios, simulations, project-based learning, and flipped classrooms among others.

In addition, Earl and Katz (2006) categorise these assessment roles according to their purpose of assessment, distinguishing assessment practices from three different perspectives: *assessment of learning*, *assessment for learning*, and *assessment as learning*. The first is related, mostly, to summative assessment and the latter two on formative assessment practices.

Succinctly, the three assessment practices can be described as: 1) *assessment of learning* usually takes place at the end of a task, unit of work, etc. and its purpose is mainly summative; 2) *assessment for learning* puts the shift from summative to formative assessment and assessment happens during the learning, often more than once, rather than at the end. It is an interactive process, and 3) *assessment as learning* is understood as a process where teachers construct and use assessments to allow students to think about and monitor their learning and develop internal feedback or self-monitoring mechanisms to validate and question their judgements (Fernandes et al., 2021).

In this process of assessment, it is also important to remember that all students have different learning styles (Felder & Silverman, 1988) and a "one-size-fits-all" solution will always exclude students from a fair and personalised assessment solution. To avoid this, teachers must use as many different assessment methods as possible, also attending to the balance of teachers and students' workload (Alves et al., 2021; Alves & Uebe-Mansur, 2018).

As Cartesian and fragmented thinking is still predominant in academic graduation environments, diagnostic and formative assessments are usually ignored by many teachers, who emphasise spot summative assessments considering them a full and effective way to verify a student's apprentice. This assessment approach is in the opposite direction of what Morin (2003) and Kleim (2000) claim about the urge to think in an academic environment more complex, where interdisciplinary in the subjects and transdisciplinary related to humanity themes are urgent in the 21st-century school model. Finding ways to re-think the learning and assessment model, considering the complexity of human beings and not only the fragmented and Cartesian point of view that considers isolated themes and assessment moments is crucial.

2.2 Gamification

Gamification is not a serious game like many examples provided in the literature, namely, (Alves, 2018; Hotta et al., 2024; Sousa et al., 2014; Witeck & Alves, 2020; Zhonggen, 2019) but it uses game elements and mechanics in non-game contexts (Khaldi et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2023). It makes use of goals, levels, stages progression, challenges, status, leader board, and feedback among others, as a way to make the most attractive and challenging activities.

Zichermann and Linder (2013) defined the term gamification as "using game-based mechanics, aesthetics and game thinking to engage people, motivate action, promote learning and solve problems.". They added that the goal is to create a system in which learners, players, consumers, and employees engage in an abstract challenge, defined by rules, interactivity, and feedback that results in a quantifiable outcome ideally eliciting an emotional reaction. And, among describing elements of this definition, they described the "game-based element" which means something where people want to invest their brain share, time, and energy.

According to the Liu et al. (2023) study, gamification group participants were more likely to engage in proactive behaviours such as contributing and asking more questions in class, interacting with their peers, arriving early to class, spending more time studying and being more proactive with mentorship. In addition, they concluded

that a learning environment enriched with game design elements specifically evokes curiosity, improving learning outcomes for learners.

According to Kapp (2012), gamification uses innovations from game design, loyalty programs, and behavioural economics. This same author said that gamification presents the best tools humanity has ever invented to create and sustain engagement in people. He also said that gamification is a proven approach using breakthroughs in technology and design to vastly improve the world, as we know it - and deliver the organisational success you desire. This is a practice that has been gaining attention in several sectors, for example, education, marketing, economics, medicine and the military sector (Chapman & Rich, 2018; Costa et al., 2021; Kapp, 2012; Markopoulos et al., 2015; Zichermann & Linder, 2013). Zichermann and Linder (2013) referred to a survey where 55% of people would be interested in working for a company offering games as a way to increase productivity.

Although the gamification benefits are well known, being presented in the previous paragraphs, some design and application difficulties appear, namely, choosing the right combination of game elements that remains a challenge for gamification designers and practitioners due to the lack of proven design approaches (Khaldi et al., 2023). The same author said there is no "one-size-fits-all" approach that works regardless of the gamification context.

3 The gamified self-made students' summative assessment (gSSA)

The gamified self-made students' summative assessment (gSSA) results from a case study that occurred during the first semester of 2024 with all of the 20 students enrolled in the Business Administration discipline from the Bachelor of System Information at Fluminense Federal Institute.

The discipline of Business Administration brings theoretical knowledge related to the four business functions: planning, organisation, driving, and controlling. During the classes, the teacher guided the students to previously watch videos concerning the content of the classes and comment on related issues or interesting aspects, according to the Flipped Classroom (FC) and Problem-based Learning (PBL) pedagogical approach. The teacher got the videos on YouTube Playlist as available at: <https://youtu.be/ykmS6V1Wmrl?si=EvlapJbfpdlABZV1>. The general aspects related to the FC and PBL are not the main focus of this paper, only the gSSA..

The proposition of FC and formative assessments (FA) occurred innovatively for this kind of theoretical discipline. For this reason, the summative assessment does not have the same importance usually considered in traditional expository learning methods (TELM), being one more among other assessments for the discipline. Related to the discipline grades, the range goes from 0 to 10, being six points as the average to be approved.

On the first day of class, the discipline teacher informed the students about gSSA, explaining the general idea and deciding the rules together with the students. From this discussion, the students decided on these general rules:

- a) four teams with five members each;
- b) four objective questions for each team, totalling 16 questions at all;
- c) each round is driven by a team that asks four questions to the opponent teams;
- d) each team needs to answer 12 questions (equivalent to three rounds with four questions);
- e) each right question is equivalent to one point;
- f) as each team can obtain 12 points in total and the maximum grade is 10 (according to the syllabus), each team can make two incorrect answers, and yet obtain the maximum grade;
- g) each question has four possible answers, being one of them correct;
- h) set time question answering is four minutes (Kahoot's time limit);

- i) The source of data for the questions development is the YouTube playlist, the available eBook, and video comments made by cohorts on the videos from the YouTube playlist;
- j) only one player will represent the entire team.

Further to the one point by the right question e), Kahoot can be set to classify the teams in each round according to their agility to the correct answer. This option is not mandatory but is interesting as a tiebreaker criterion.

The rule j) concerns how questions are answered and team members' participation in each round and considers two possibilities. In the first possibility, only one team member represents the whole team in each round from a consensus to the right answer. The advantage is the process simplification since each question would have three answers (one for each group). The disadvantage is that members lose the opportunity to disagree with the rest of the team. The second possibility is each round could potentially involve all team members submitting individual answers. The advantage is the independence of each member to answer the question without the need to vote or agree with a general team consensus. The disadvantage is that the process became more difficult to drive because each team member would be computed separately.

Further, the general rules above were defined together with the students, the rules below were compulsory and dealt with some specific aspects of the gSSA. To encourage team members to study and create more thoughtful questions, the following rule was implemented:

- k) the opposing team has the opportunity to challenge any questions. If the opposing team successfully identifies an error in the question, they are awarded one point without having to provide an answer. However, if they are incorrect in their challenge, they lose one point.

To avoid teams cheating (for instance, sharing the questions among them in a way that all teams obtain the maximum grade by the previous knowledge of the opponent's correct answer), the following rule was established:

- l) if the team that answered the question incorrectly does not get the correct answer, the point for that question is awarded to the team that wrote the question.

The institution mandates that teachers assign an Individual Global Score (IGS) between 0 and 10 to each student. Students must achieve a minimum score of 6 to pass the syllabus without additional assessment. To meet this requirement, the teacher and students agreed on the following grading system: 60% of the final grade will be based on the average score of weekly tasks completed throughout the semester, and 40% will be based on the team score obtained from the gSSA.

The 40% team score, decided between the teacher and students, was as follows: the first-place team members received 10 points, second place received 8 points, third place received 6 points, and all other teams received 5 points. Figure 1 illustrates the IGS composition:

Figure 1. Individual Global Score composition.

4 Result Analysis

Despite the possibility of running the rounds manually analogously, the Kahoot app was the choice for running the rounds. According to *What Is Kahoot! | How to Play Kahoot!*, the app " (...) is a game-based learning platform that makes it easy to create, share and play learning games or trivia quizzes in minutes".

The advantage of the choice comes from Kahoot's feature that automatically bonus the faster player to correctly answer a question, eliminating the need for a stopwatch. The faster player bonus to correctly answer a question is not a mandatory rule by Kahoot, but promotes a sense of urgency among the teams and increases the player's capability to assert and correct thinking under stress, as also provides a qualitative aspect further the quantitative, obtained from correct answers.

The benefit of using "Kahoot!" is its automatic bonus feature, which rewards the fastest player to answer correctly. This eliminates the need for a stopwatch and promotes a sense of urgency among teams, enhancing players' ability to think quickly and accurately under pressure. Additionally, it adds a qualitative measure to the quantitative one based on correct answers. Although not mandatory, this feature encourages strategic thinking and improves overall performance.

A free public Kahoot account has some limitations, like a limit of 50 players in the same game and a limit of 120 characters. The player limit was not a problem due to the rule j). The character limit forced the students to develop their synthesis ability.

From these limitations, the gSSA explored in this paper consisted of four rounds (one for each team) with four questions per team (according to the rules a) to l), as followed by the team names:

- Team 1: *Seu Potencial* (SP);
- Team 2: SGC;
- Team 3: e-book;
- Team 4: VAPE.

At each round, a team proposes four questions (4 minutes/for each one), and the three others answer them, totalling four questions per round (16 minutes/total). As each team needs to participate in three rounds (total of team - 1), each team will have 12 questions to answer at the final of the three rounds. The estimated time for the four rounds is approximately one hour. Including the interval between the rounds for the teams to set up their games, the estimated time is approximately 1 hour and a half. Figure 2 shows the kind of question developed by a team among others.

Figure 2: Examples of teams' questions on the Kahoot app

Figure 3 shows how the results for each round were calculated on a whiteboard. The researcher's choice to present the results as an image instead of a table, to show that it is possible to compute the results in learning environments where digital technology is not present.

The table's columns represent the four-question round driven by each team. The rows represent one of the four questions to the team's opponents. Each cell contains the Kahoot score for each team according to their agility to the correct answer, as also the indication if the questions were answered correctly (✓) or incorrectly (✗). If Kahoot is not used or this Kahoot feature is not set, only rule e) is considered. The last column contains the team classification according to Kahoot's fast-correct answer feature. The last row has the team's number of correct answers by round and the total number of correct answers according to the rule e).

EQUIPE	SEU POTENCIAL	SGC	ebook	VAPE	TOTAL
1	VAPE 847 ✓ EBOOK 755 ✓ SGC 710 ✓	SP-986 ✓ VAPE-851 ✓ EBOOK-0 ✗	SGC-921 ✓ SP-883 ✓ VAPE-859 ✓	SP-994 ✓ SGC-977 ✓ EBOOK-0 ✗	
2	VAPE 1788 ✓ EBOOK 1621 ✓ SGC 1577 ✓	SP-1922 ✓ VAPE-851 ✗ EBOOK-0 ✗	SGC-1869 ✓ VAPE-1823 ✓ SP-1811 ✓	SP-1968 ✓ SGC-1941 ✓ EBOOK-965 ✓	
3	X	SP-2682 ✓ VAPE-1704 ✓ EBOOK-896 ✓	VAPE-2793 ✓ SGC-2792 ✓ SP-2721 ✓	SGC-2891 ✓ SP-1968 ✓ EBOOK-1793 ✓	
4	VAPE 1788 ✓ EBOOK 1621 ✗ SGC 1577 ✗	SP-3580 ✓ VAPE-2516 ✓ EBOOK-1846 ✓	VAPE-3773 ✓ SGC-3729 ✓ SP-2721 ✗	EBOOK-2612 ✓ SP-2947 ✓ SGC-3856 ✓	VAPE-8077 (8) SP-9248 (1) EBOOK-6084 (14) SGC-9162 (2)
PONTOS (ACERTOS)	VAPE - 3 EBOOK - 3 SGC - 3 SP - 1	SP - 4 VAPE - 3 EBOOK - 2	VAPE - 4 SGC - 4 SP - 3	EBOOK - 3 SP - 4 SGC - 4	VAPE - 10 SP - 12 SGC - 11 EBOOK - 8

Figure 3: Teams results in the whiteboard from gSSA

The opponent teams decided that "SP" team would lose their 3rd round opportunity (Figure 3, second column, fourth row) because their question violated the previously established rules for questions, proposition. The Table 1 shows the final results for Individual points from gSSA team ranking (according to the Figure 1).

Table 1: Teams' metrics

Team	Ranking	Hits (Kahoot) / efficacy	Score (Kahoot)	Grade (gSSA)
SP	1	12 / 100%	9248	10
SGC	2	11 / 92%	9162	8
VAPE	3	10 / 83%	8077	6
E-book	4	8 / 67%	6048	5

Despite a summative assessment, students were very involved, and it was funny, as usual in the game competitions. The results presented in Table 1 shows the students in their majority acquired and understood the class content due in a scenario where gSSA would be the only assessment method, $\frac{3}{4}$ (75%) of the students achieved a minimum grade of 6 to pass the syllabus without recovery class test.

During the experiment, the students were actively engaged in the learning process, as they were required to create questions in a peer-assessment style format, which went beyond the traditional method of memorising content for a written test. This allowed them to evaluate their understanding of the material. Additionally, they completed two self-assessment surveys regarding their learning perception. The method lessened the teacher's workload by decentralising the creation of the summative assessment. This was achieved by having the students develop and censor the assessment's questions by themselves (as the penalty for the "SP" team).

The experiment described in this paper fostered an assessment complex environment, as evidenced by five aspects of Complex Thinking (Uébe-Mansur, 2011; Morin, 2007). These aspects are: a) Hologrammatic: Students were not only responsible for passively answering a survey, but for actively creating it; b) Recursivity: Some students independently developed innovative solutions without prior prompting; c) Reintroduction: Students learned from both their successes and mistakes, not only while playing the game but also during its development; d) Dialogic: Dichotomous aspects like assessment and fun were integrated; e) Systemic View: A holistic perspective of the process and subjects was formed through rules agreed upon by participants. These aspects were also evidenced in other related pedagogical experiences, namely Alves & Soares (2020); Soares & Alves (2021) and Hotta et al. (2024).

5 Conclusion

This paper presented a summative assessment developed by the students, under the Complex Thinking approach. By doing this, students become responsible for their own learning and assessment, developed innovative solutions, learning from their own mistakes, they had fun and were involved in the process. This summative assessment was only one part of the teaching process, which adopted interactive and engaging methods to explore theoretical concepts with students. Due to space constraints, other aspects of this experience, such as the learning methodology and formative assessments, it will be presented in future work.

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References

- Alves, A. C. (2018). U-Shaped Cells Operating Modes: a Review and a Hands-on Simulation Comparison. *International Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management*, 9(2), 87–97. <https://doi.org/10.24867/IJIE-2018-2-110>
- Alves, A. C., Fernandes, S., & Uebe-Mansur, A. F. (2021). Online assessment: more student cheating than on-site? *PAEE/ALE'2021, International Conference on Active Learning in Engineering Education, 13rd International Symposium on Project Approaches in Engineering Education (PAEE) and 18th Active Learning in Engineering Education Workshop (ALE)*, Braga, Portugal, 15–22. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5095020>
- Alves, A. C., & Uebe-Mansur, A. F. (2018). PBL methodology in business administration, and industrial engineering and management programs: Similarities and differences. *International Symposium on Project Approaches in Engineering Education*, 8, 240–248.
- Alves, Anabela C., & Soares, F. (2020). Interdisciplinary contents integration and key competences developed in a project work of Industrial Engineering and Management third year. *PAEE/ALE'2020, International Conference on Active Learning in Engineering Education, 12th International Symposium on Project Approaches in Engineering Education (PAEE) and 17th Active Learning in Engineering Education Workshop (ALE)*, 21–30. https://zenodo.org/record/4782460/files/PAEE_ALE_2020_PROCEEDINGS_submission_40.pdf
- Alves, A. C., & van Hattum-Janssen, N. (2022). *Training Engineering Students for Modern Technological Advancement* (A. C. Alves & N. van Hattum-Janssen (eds.)). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-8816-1>
- Chapman, J. R., & Rich, P. J. (2018). Does educational gamification improve students' motivation? If so, which game elements work best? *Journal of Education for Business*, 93(7), 315–322. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08832323.2018.1490687>
- Costa, H. G., Sheremetieff, F. H., & Araújo, E. A. (2021). Influence of Game-Based Methods in Developing Engineering Competences. In *Training Engineering Students for Modern Technological Advancement* (pp. 69–88). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-8816-1.ch004>

- Earl, L. and Katz, S. (2006) Rethinking Classroom Assessment with Purpose in Mind: Assessment for Learning, Assessment as Learning, Assessment of Learning. Canada: Manitoba Education, Citizenship and Youth, Winnipeg. https://www.edu.gov.mb.ca/k12/assess/wncp/full_doc.pdf
- Felder, R., & Silverman, L. (1988). Learning and Teaching Styles in Engineering Education. *Engineering Education*, 78(7), 674–681.
- Fernandes, S., Alves, A. C., & Uebe-Mansur, A. F. (2021). Student-Centered Assessment Practices. In A. S. Moura, P. Reis, & M. N. D. S. Cordeiro (Eds.), *Handbook of Research on Determining the Reliability of Online Assessment and Distance Learning* (pp. 213–243). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-4769-4.ch009>
- Hadji, C. (1994). Assessment, Rules of the Game. From Intentions to Instruments. (In Portuguese: *A Avaliação, Regras do Jogo. Das Intenções aos Instrumentos*). Porto Editora.
- Hotta, B. Y., Machado, B. A., Souza, F. B. de, Lima, P. A. B., & Alves, A. C. (2024). Game-based learning in engineering education: Using the Goldratt Simulator to learn about the theory of constraints. *Revista Gestão Da Produção Operações e Sistemas*, 1. <https://doi.org/10.15675/gepros.3002>
- Kleim, E., J. (2000). Complexity of assessment, assessment of Complexity (In Portuguese: Complexidade da avaliação, avaliação da Complexidade). In *EccoS Revista Científica*. <http://doi.org/10.558/eccos.v2i2.224>
- Kapp, K. M. (2012). *The Gamification of Learning and Instruction: Game-based Methods and Strategies for Training and Education*. John Wiley & Sons. https://books.google.pt/books?id=CV0rUvnyrkWC&pg=PR15&hl=pt-PT&source=gbs_selected_pages&cad=1#v=onepage&q&f=false
- Khaldi, A., Bouzidi, R., & Nader, F. (2023). Gamification of e-learning in higher education: a systematic literature review. *Smart Learning Environments*, 10(1), 10. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-023-00227-z>
- Lima, R. M., Villas-Boas, V., Soares, F., Carneiro, O. S., Ribeiro, P., & Mesquita, D. (2024). Mapping the implementation of active learning approaches in a school of engineering – the positive effect of teacher training. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 49(5), 945–964. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2024.2313541>
- Liu, S., Ma, G., Tewogbola, P., Gu, X., Gao, P., Dong, B., He, D., Lai, W., & Wu, Y. (2023). Game principle: enhancing learner engagement with gamification to improve learning outcomes. *Journal of Workplace Learning*, 35(5), 450–462.
- Markopoulos, A. P., Fragkou, A., Kasidiaris, P. D., & Davim, J. P. (2015). Gamification in engineering education and professional training. *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering Education*, 43(2), 118–131.
- Morin, E., Montuori, A. (2008). *On Complexity* (Advances in Systems Theory, Complexity, and the Human Sciences). New York: Hampton Press.
- Morin, E. (2007). *Introduction to Complex Thinking*. Porto Alegre: Sulina.
- Morin, E. (2003) *A well-made head: rethinking reform, reforming thinking*, Rio de Janeiro: ed, Bertrand
- Rieg, D. L., Lima, R. M. M., Mesquita, D., Scramim, F. C. L., & Mattasoglio Neto, O. (2022). Active learning strategies to develop research competences in engineering education. *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*, 14(3), 1210–1223. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JARHE-01-2021-0038>
- Soares, F., & Alves, A. C. (2021, November 1). Learning While Playing or Playing While Learning? *Volume 9: Engineering Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1115/IMECE2021-68801>
- Sousa, R. M., Alves, A. C., Moreira, F., & Dinis-Carvalho, J. (2014). Lean games and hands-on approaches as learning tools for students and professionals. *7th International Conference on Production Research - Americas*.
- Uebe-Mansur, A. F., & Alves, A. C. (2018). The importance of peer assessment and self-assessment in PBL applied to an administration course. *Revista Ibero-Americana de Estudos Em Educação*, 13(esp1), 451–467. <https://periodicos.fclar.unesp.br/iberoamericana/article/view/10347/7302>
- Uebe-Mansur, A. F., & Alves, A. C. (2020). A influência dos modelos de produção industrial nas mudanças culturais e educacionais das sociedades (in English: The influence of industrial production models on cultural and educational changes in societies). In *Cultura, Educação e Movimentos Sociais: experiências e questões para o século XXI* (pp. 41–64). EDITORA CRV. <https://doi.org/10.24824/978655578255.4.41-64>
- What is Kahoot? | How to play Kahoot! ([s.d.]). Kahoot! Recuperado 12 de novembro de 2024, de <https://kahoot.com/what-is-kahoot/>
- Witeck, G., & Alves, A. C. (2020). Developing lean competencies through serious games. *PAEE/ALE'2020, International Conference on Active Learning in Engineering Education, 12th International Symposium on Project Approaches in Engineering Education (PAEE) and 17th Active Learning in Engineering Education Workshop (ALE)*, 179–186. https://zenodo.org/record/4816183/files/PAEE_ALE_2020_PROCEEDINGS_submission_198.pdf
- Zhonggen, Y. (2019). A Meta-Analysis of Use of Serious Games in Education over a Decade. *International Journal of Computer Games Technology*, 2019, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/4797032>
- Zichermann, G., & Linder, J. (2013). *The Gamification Revolution*. McGraw-Hill. https://books.google.pt/books?id=M2Rb9ZtFxcc&pg=PA1&hl=pt-PT&source=gbs_toc_r&cad=2#v=onepage&q&f=false